

SEAWEEDS AS NUTRACEUTICALS FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND DISEASE PREVENTION**GADHIYA SONAL**

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ABSTRACT

In recent year, Marine organisms including seaweeds are one of the important marine living resources in the world. Seaweed act as primary producer in food chain and used traditionally and consumed as part of daily diet. Seaweed contains bio-molecules such as protein, carbohydrates, minerals and vitamins. Presently fresh, dried and processed seaweeds are utilized for human consumption, and because of that it is called as medicinal food in 21st century. Several studies have demonstrated the seaweeds contain a various property like an antibacterial property, antiviral, antistress, anti-inflammatory, anti- carcinogenic, anti-tumor and antithrombotic. These include fiber, anti- oxidant, mineral and omega-3 fatty acids. In some epidemiological studies, the lower incidence of chronic disease, such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, and their risk factors in this part of the world has been related to healthier diet profile associated with seaweed consumption.

Keywords: -

Seaweed, Nutraceutical properties, Medicinal food, Human health, biomolecules

INTRODUCTION

Only macroscopic, multicellular marine red, green, and brown algae are typically referred to as "seaweeds" (Lobban *et al.*, 1994). Edible seaweeds (macroalgae) have the potential to supply a rich and sustainable source of macronutrients and micronutrients to the human diet, especially in regions where seaweed plays a substantial role in regular meals, such as Japan, where seaweed accounts for roughly one-fifth of all meals. Seaweed consumption in Western diets has long been limited to artisanal practices and coastal communities, but the health-food business has piqued public interest in recent years (Cherry *et al.*, 2019).

Seaweed is a low-calorie food that is high in vitamins, minerals, and vital trace elements, as well as polyunsaturated fatty acids, bioactive metabolites, proteins, polysaccharides, and dietary fiber. Many studies have promoted the health benefits of seaweed supplementation alongside a regular diet, in addition to regular consumption. Consumption of seaweed on a regular basis lowered depressive symptoms in pregnant Japanese women and reduced the chance of suicide in adults. In the Korean population, frequent ingestion of dietary seaweeds reduced the risk of diabetes mellitus (Ganesan *et al.*, 2019).

- (1) For example, seaweeds are used for treatment and or for prevention of goitre, which is caused by the lack of iodine in the diet (L. Rosenfeld, 2000).
- (2) A clinical study found that women who consume *Undaria* seaweed on a regular basis have a lower risk of breast cancer (Teas *et al.*, 2013).

Seaweeds as nutraceutical properties

Seaweeds include bioactive compounds such as polysaccharides, peptides, phytochemicals, vitamins, and fatty acids, which can be added to diets to make fortified or functional foods, or manufactured into nutritional supplements (Suleria *et al.*, 2015). Seaweeds have long been thought to play a role in cancer prevention, tumour progression, and even health recovery following radiotherapy or chemotherapy (Délérís *et al.*, 2016). Seaweed consumption has been related to a lower risk of chronic diseases like cancer, hyperlipidemia, and coronary heart disease (CHD), based on epidemiological research comparing Japanese and Western diets. Seaweed usage in Japan has been estimated at 5.3 grammes per day. lipids from seaweeds may have therapeutic characteristics related to heart disease, in addition to other bioactive substances found in many seaweed species. Algal oils, like other oils produced from the sea, have anti-inflammatory properties.

Use of various species of seaweeds in human health and disease prevention

- 1) ***Caulerpa racemose*** :- This alga can be used in diet foods to help people lose weight. *Caulerpa* was also used in traditional medicine to alleviate rheumatism and lower blood pressure. *Caulerpa racemosa* is a mineral-rich, vitamin-rich, fiber-rich, and antioxidant-rich plant (Fithrian, 2015).
- 2) ***Kappaphycus alvarezii***: Reduces total cholesterol, LDL, and triacylglycerol levels while increasing HDL-C levels (Matanjun, 2010).
- 3) ***U. pinnatifida*** (Mekabu): *U. pinnatifida* (Mekabu) also exhibited high anticancer activity against breast cancer cells in vivo and in vitro (Délérís *et al.*, 2016).
- 4) ***Sargassum wightii***: In Chinese medicine, this seaweed is traditionally used to cure goitre (Mohapatra *et al.*, 2016).
- 5) ***Caulerpa lentillifera***: Dipeptidyl peptidase-IV and -glucosidase enzymes are decreased. Insulin secretion is increased (Sharma and Rhyu, 2014).
- 6) ***U. pinnatifida*, *S. horneri*, and *C. hakodatensi*** : Inhibits lipid hydroperoxide levels. (Grasa-López *et al.*, 2016)
- 7) ***Gelidium amansii***: inhibits adipogenesis and decreases the expression of adipogenic genes (Kang *et al.*, 2017).
- 8) **Brown seaweed**:inhibits triglyceride formation and cholesterol balance in HepG2 cells (Nagappan *et al.*, 2017).
- 9) ***Porphyria dentate***: Increased plasma insulin secretion and lower plasma glucose levels (Chao *et al.*, 2014).
- 10) ***Asparagopsis taxiformis* and *Sarconema sp.***:- controlling goiter disease caused by enlargement of thyroid gland (Reddy, 2012).
- 11) ***Gracilaria crassa*, *Laurencia papillosa* and *Turbinaria ornate***:- have anti-ulcer, wound-healing, and hepatoprotective properties in their research, they discovered that *L. papillosa* provided the best protection (81%) against gastric ulcers, followed by *Gracilaria crassa* (76%) and ranitidine (90%). (Pati, 2016).
- 12) ***Fucus evanescens* and *Fucus vesiculosus*** :- Anticoagulant, antioxidant , Anticancer, antimetastatic (Gomez-Zavaglia, *et al.*, 2019).

Seaweeds contain a varies bioactive compound

No.	Bioactive compound	Use in disease prevention	Reference
1	Fucoidan	Fucoidans can be found in a variety of brown seaweed species. Fucoidan has been shown to suppress matrix breakdown, particularly matrix metalloproteinases. Fucoidans, which can be found in a variety of seaweeds, have been shown to slow tumour development.	Déléris <i>et al.</i> , 2016
2	Alginates	Brown seaweeds have alginates in them. Alginate protects against carcinogens by removing them from the digestive system and shielding the stomach and intestinal surface membranes from their effects, hence increasing dietary fiber absorption. Alginate, which comes from seaweeds, is also utilized as a biomaterial in capsules, nanoparticles, and gels to contain and deliver active substances that could be used to treat diseases like cancer.	Déléris <i>et al.</i> , 2016
3	Fucoxanthin	The anticancer properties of fucoxanthin and its deacetylated metabolite are numerous. Brown seaweeds and diatoms both contain it. Several investigations in cell lines and in animals show that fucoxanthin has antiproliferative and cancer-preventive properties.	Déléris <i>et al.</i> , 2016
4	Carrageenan	Carraguard, a non-spermicidal microbicide containing carrageenan, a red seaweed derivative, has just been clinically evaluated and found to be a potential product for inhibiting HIV/AIDS transmission and lowering the chance of women catching the disease.	Reddy, 2012
5	Ulvan	Iduronic acid is abundant in ulvan. Iduronic acid is utilized in the manufacture of anti-thrombotic heparin fragment analogues.	Vázquez-Rodríguez, and Amaya-Guerra, 2016.
6	Phlorotannins	Brown seaweeds contain the most phlorotannins. Phlorotannins are well-known for their anti-cancer antioxidant properties.	Déléris <i>et al.</i> , 2016
7	polyphenols, flavonoids and polysaccharides	Brown, red, and green algae have been found to have antioxidant and antibacterial properties.	Reddy, 2012
8	Laminarin	Laminarin, also known as laminaran, is an active component obtained from the dried thallus of brown seaweeds such as <i>Laminaria japonica</i> , <i>Ecklonia kurome</i> , and <i>Eisenia bicyclis</i> . As a result, laminarin contributes to dietary fibre intake and helps to prevent cancer.	Déléris <i>et al.</i> , 2016
9	Others (Vitamins, amino acids, proteins, etc. are important components in the seaweed plant structure	Can be separated and used as nutraceuticals, but are best consumed as part of a seaweed diet.	Qin, Y, 2018

CONCLUSION

Seaweeds are one of the world's most important marine resources. Seaweed is a medical food for the twenty-first century since it is good for human health. Many researches have backed up the health benefits of taking seaweed supplements in addition to a healthy diet. Several studies have shown that seaweeds have a variety of qualities, including antibacterial, antiviral, antistress, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, anti-tumor, and antithrombotic capabilities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to thank Dr. D.T. Vaghela, Professor and Head of Dept. aquatic resource Management and also thanks to College of Fisheries science, Veraval, Junagadh Agricultural University, for encouragement and suggestions during the investigation during this study.

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